

A Macrocyclic PycLen-Based Gd³⁺ Complex with High Relaxivity and pH Response

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ABSTRACT: We report the synthesis and characterization of the macrocyclic ligand 2,2'-((2-(3,9-bis(carboxymethyl)-3,6,9-triazolo[2,6]-pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-yl)ethyl)azanediyl)diacetic acid (H₄L) and several of its complexes with the lanthanide ions. The structure of the free ligand was determined using X-ray diffraction measurements. Two N atoms of the pycLen moiety in *trans* position are protonated in the solid state, together with the exocyclic N atom and one of the carboxylate groups of the ligand. The relaxivity of the Gd³⁺ complex was found to increase from 6.7 mM⁻¹ s⁻¹ at pH 8.6 to 8.5 mM⁻¹ s⁻¹ below pH ~ 6.0. Luminescence lifetime measurements recorded from H₂O and D₂O solutions of the Eu³⁺ complex evidence the presence of a single complex species in solution at low pH (~5.0) that contains two inner-sphere water molecules. DFT calculations suggest that the coordination environment of the Ln³⁺ ion is fulfilled by the four N atoms of the pycLen unit, two oxygen atoms of the macrocyclic acetate groups and an oxygen atom of an exocyclic carboxylate group. The two inner-sphere water molecules complete coordination number nine around the metal ion. At high pH (~9.3) the lifetime of the excited ⁵D₀ level of Eu³⁺ displays a bi-exponential behavior that can be attributed to the presence of two species in solution with hydration numbers of *q* = 0 and *q* = 1. The ¹H NMR and DOSY spectra recorded from solutions of the Eu³⁺ and Y³⁺ complexes reveal a structural change triggered by pH and the formation of small aggregates at high pH values.

INTRODUCTION

Since the approval of [Gd(DTPA)(H₂O)]²⁻ by the FDA in 1988 as the first contrast agent for clinical applications, hundreds of potential new contrast agents have been synthesized, although just a few of them are currently used on a daily basis in medicine. Most commercially available contrast agents are paramagnetic gadolinium complexes, which enhance the contrast of the image by shortening the magnetic relaxation time of the water protons in the surrounding tissues where they distribute. The efficiency of a paramagnetic complex to enhance the relaxation of water proton nuclei is generally characterized *in vitro* by its relaxivity, which normalizes the effect to a 1 mM concentration of the paramagnetic ion.¹⁻³

The design of new contrast agents needs to fulfill some requirements such as: 1) thermodynamic and kinetic stability, a

particularly important issue since the documentation of nephrogenic systemic fibrosis (NSF), an illness detected in patients with renal impairment after administration of certain contrast agents;⁴⁻⁶ 2) High relaxivity, which allows the use of lower doses of the contrast agent and the detection of low-concentration targets.^{8,9} 3) Good solubility, as contrast agents are injected in rather large doses due to the low sensitivity of the technique.⁸ 4) Rapid excretion to minimize the chances of complex dissociation and the consequent risk of deposition, and 5) Low osmolality and viscosity to avoid adverse reactions and necrosis of the tissue.¹⁰

Several strategies have been developed to achieve high relaxivities by optimizing the inner-sphere contribution to proton relaxivity.¹¹ The inner-sphere relaxivity is governed at the

magnetic fields used for clinical scanners (1.5 T and 3 T)¹ and biomedical research (usually up to 9.4 T)¹ by three main parameters: the mean residence time of coordinated water molecules in the Gd³⁺ coordination sphere (τ_M),^{11,12} the rotational correlation time (τ_R)¹³ and the number of water molecules directly coordinated to the metal ion (q).² The increase in q is generally achieved by decreasing the denticity of the ligand, which may result in a decreased complex stability. However, certain bis-hydrated complexes were found to present good stability profiles, sometimes comparable or even better than those of related $q = 1$ complexes.¹⁴⁻¹⁹

The toxicity of gadolinium(III) ions requires suitable chelating agents that provide thermodynamic stable and kinetically inert complexes.⁸ This is usually achieved using open chain polyamines or polyazamacrocycles conveniently functionalized.²⁰ Pyridine-based macrocyclic ligands have shown to bind efficiently lanthanide (III) ions with the affinity being strongly affected by the ring size.^{21,22} Twelve-membered rings with acetate or phosphonate side arms yield very stable complexes.²³⁻²⁶ The pyridine in the macrocycle increases the stereochemical rigidity of the resulting complexes, a property often associated with an increase in their kinetic inertness.^{8,24,27} The pyridine moiety may also provide a suitable site for a further functionalization,²⁸⁻³⁰ which facilitates molecular recognition of specific targets. Furthermore, a bis-hydrated Gd³⁺ complex derived from pyclen containing α -functionalized acetate arms is currently under development as an extracellular MRI contrast agent,³¹ as it presents a high relaxivity, remarkable kinetic inertness and a pharmacokinetic profile similar to those of commercially available contrast agents.³²

Chart 1. Structures of the ligands discussed in this work.

A huge amount of research in the field of MRI contrast agents has been devoted to develop systems that present response to relevant biochemical parameters, as for instance pH,³³⁻³⁷ the concentration of biogenic cations³⁸⁻⁴⁹ or neurotransmitters,⁵⁰⁻⁵³ enzymatic activity⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶ or redox potential.⁵⁷⁻⁶³ Among these physiological parameters pH is considered to be

an important biomarker of several diseases, including inflammatory processes and cancer.^{64,65} Most pH-responsive Gd³⁺ agents contain a group coordinated to the metal ion (i. e. sulfonamide, amine, *p*-nitrophenol, phosphonate...) that is detached upon protonation close to physiological pH. This often results in an increased relaxivity associated with the increased number of water molecules in the first coordination sphere. Alternatively, pH response may be achieved by modulation of τ_R .⁶⁶

Macrocyclic ligands based on the pyclen backbone such as PCTA (2,2',2''-[3,6,9,15-tetraazabicyclo[9.3.1]pentadecan-1(15),11,13-triene-3,6,9-triyl]triacetic acid)⁶⁷ and derivatives containing picolinate pendant arms replacing one or two of the acetate groups of PCTA (i. e. H₃L1, Chart 1) were found to form lanthanide complexes presenting interesting photophysical and relaxometric properties, including rather high stability constants, slow dissociation kinetics and high emission quantum yields of the Eu³⁺ and particularly Tb³⁺ complexes.^{68,69} Herein we report a new derivative of PCTA and several of its lanthanide complexes. This new scorpionand macrocycle (denoted as H₄L, Chart 1) incorporates an iminodiacetate tail that may contribute to the coordination of lanthanide ions. We report the X-ray structure of the ligand, the physicochemical characterization of the Eu³⁺ complex and a full relaxometric study of the Gd³⁺ complex, which presents response to pH within the biologically relevant pH range. NMR and DFT studies were conducted to rationalize the unexpected relaxivity response to pH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ligand synthesis and characterization. The synthesis of the new pyridine-based contrast agent was carried out by a modification of the Richman-Atkins procedure where perysilylated tris(2-aminoethyl)amine (TREN-Ts) and 2,6-bis(bromomethyl)pyridine were refluxed in a 1:1 ratio in CH₃CN using K₂CO₃ as a base, following the procedure described previously.^{70,71} Deprotection of the tosyl groups was achieved in acidic HBr/HAc media and phenol to obtain the hydrobromic salt. Later functionalization with potassium chloroacetate obtained from chloroacetic acid and potassium hydroxide afforded the tetra acetic acid derivative after column chromatography (DOWEX 1X8, formate form).

Crystals of H₄L suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by slow diffusion of ethanol into a solution of the ligand in water. The unit cell has a β angle very close to 90°, so initially

it was assumed to be orthorhombic. The structure could be solved in the Pmcn space group, but the result contained an unnatural mirror plane. A closer look revealed that the right space group was monoclinic $P2_1/c$ with $\beta = 90.009(3)$, and that the structure is a twin with two components which are mirrored to one another. The twin fraction was refined, the result being 0.476(1), which approximates to a perfect twin.

The asymmetric unit contains one unit of the ligand L along with a number of water molecules. The molecule of L contains a total of four protons, since it had been synthesized as H_4L and no other atoms are present in the crystal except solvent molecules. Three of those protons were found in the Fourier map on nitrogen atoms N2, N4 and N5 (Figure 1). The location of the fourth proton was decided by analyzing bond lengths of the carboxylate moieties and located on O8 (Figure S1, Supporting Information). This means that the H_4L moiety holds a total of six charges; three positive (on N2, N4 and N5) and three negative (on carboxylates C15, C17 and C19). The three charged carboxylates are oriented towards the same side of the molecule (see Figure 1) and all three of them contain an intramolecular hydrogen bond with the nearest protonated nitrogen (see Table S1, Supporting Information), while at the same time they form a rich hydrogen bond network with a number of water molecules (see Figure S2, Supporting Information). The protonated carboxylate also forms hydrogen bonds with both a water molecule and the same group of a neighbor $H_4L^{3+/3-}$ entity. In addition to hydrogen bond interactions, electrostatic forces seem to play an important role in the packing. Molecules of $H_4L^{3+/3-}$ pack with each other along an antiparallel orientation with their neighbors in such a manner that positive and negative charges are aligned (see Figure S3, Supporting Information).

The protonation of the two amine N atoms of the macrocyclic unit in *trans* position (N2 and N4) is in agreement with the macroscopic protonation sequence established by NMR measurements for PCTA and closely related derivatives, which indicated that the first protonation of the macrocycle occurs at the N atom in *trans* position with respect to the pyridyl N atom, as also observed in the solid state for the monoprotonated form of pycen.⁷² However, the second protonation step provokes a shift of the former proton to afford a bis-protonated species on the two *trans* amine N atoms adjacent to N3.²⁴

Figure 2. Plot of the 1H relaxivity (20 MHz, 25 °C) of GdL as a function of pH.

Proton relaxivity. The relaxivity (r_{1p}) of $[GdL]^-$ was first investigated at 25 °C and 20 MHz over a wide pH range (ca. 10 to 2). Relaxivity takes a value of $6.7 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at pH 8.6, while below pH 8.0 increases reaching a value of $8.5 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This represents a 1.8-fold increase of proton relaxivity on decreasing pH. Relaxivity remains constant in the pH range ~ 6.0 – 3.0 , indicating that the complex does not dissociate within this pH range. The relaxivity observed within the pH range 6.0 – 3.0 is very similar to that observed for pycen-based bis-aquated complexes with similar molecular weight.⁷³ Below pH 3.0, relaxivity increases as a result of complex dissociation. A noticeable decrease of r_{1p} is also observed above pH 9.0, an effect that can be attributed to the formation of hydroxo species, as suggested for different Gd^{3+} complexes⁷⁴ including PCTA derivatives.^{21,75} The analysis of the r_{1p} vs pH profile provides a pK_a of 7.01 ± 0.03 , which must be related to the protonation of the amine nitrogen atom of the iminodiacetate group, as protonation of the macrocyclic N atoms should cause complex dissociation. These results together with the hydration numbers obtained from luminescence lifetime measurements (see below) point to a change in the hydration number of the complex, from 1 at $pH > 8.0$ to 2 at $pH < 6.0$, triggered by the protonation of the ligand.

Figure 3. ^1H Nuclear Magnetic Relaxation Dispersion (NMRD) profiles of GdL recorded at pH 4.98 (top) and 9.20 (bottom). The solid lines represent the fits of the data as explained in the text.

Nuclear magnetic relaxation dispersion profiles (NMRD) were recorded at pH values of 4.98 and 9.20 to gain additional insight into the parameters that control the relaxivity of the $[\text{GdL}]^-$ and $[\text{GdHL}]$ species (Figure 3). NMRD profiles were recorded at three different temperatures (10, 25 and 37 °C) covering magnetic field strengths of 2.3×10^{-4} to 1.1 T, which correspond to proton Larmor frequencies of 0.01-60 MHz. The relaxivities recorded at both pH values decrease with increasing temperature, indicating that the fast rotation of the complexes in solution limits r_{1p} . This is typical of small Gd^{3+} complexes with short rotational correlation times (τ_R) and fast water exchange rates.⁷⁶ The relaxivities recorded at pH 4.98 are higher than those measured at high pH over the whole range of proton Larmor frequencies, which is in line with an increased hydration of the protonated form of the complex.

Photophysical properties and hydration number. The emission spectra of the Eu^{3+} complex of L were recorded at two different pH values (4.5 and 9.5) to gain information on the relaxometric behavior of the Gd^{3+} analogue. The emission spectra, recorded under excitation through the pyridyl chromophore at 273 nm, present the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_j$ transitions typical of Eu^{3+} (Figure 4).⁷⁷ The emission spectra show a single $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_0$ transition at 578.4 nm and three components for the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_1$ transition at 587.8, 591.0 and 596.6 (pH 4.5) and 588.0, 591.0 and 595.8 nm. The shape of the emission spectra does not change very much with pH, the main differences being noticed for the intensity and splitting of the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_2$ transition. The intensity of the latter transition is very sensitive to changes in the coordination environment, while the intensity of the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_1$ transition is relatively independent of the coordination environment due to its magnetic dipole character.⁷⁸ Increasing the pH results in a noticeable increase of the intensity of the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_2$ transition with respect to the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_1$ one, which signals a change in the metal coordination environment likely related to the coordination of more polarizable donor groups.^{79,80} This suggests that inner-sphere water molecules are replaced by more polarizable carboxylate donor atoms upon increasing the pH.⁸¹

Figure 4. Emission spectra of the Eu^{3+} recorded at different pH values (5×10^{-5} M, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 273$ nm).

The decay profile of the $^5\text{D}_0$ excited state measured in H_2O solution at pH 4.8 can be perfectly fitted to a monoexponential function with a lifetime of 0.384 ms, which is typical of Eu^{3+} complexes containing two coordinated water molecules.⁸² This suggests the presence of a single Eu^{3+} site in solution (Table 1, Figure 5). The emission lifetime recorded at the same pH in D_2O solution is considerably longer (2.126 ms). The lifetimes recorded in H_2O and D_2O solutions afford hydration numbers close to 2.0 using the methods proposed by Horrocks⁸³ and Beeby,⁸⁴ indicating the presence of two water molecules directly coordinated to the metal ion. Conversely, the emission lifetimes recorded at pH 9.3 cannot be fitted with monoexponential decay functions (Figure 5). The lifetimes determined in H_2O by bi-exponential fitting of the data point to the presence of a minor component (30%) with a short lifetime of 0.290 ms and a major component with a longer lifetime of 0.683 ms. Measurements in D_2O solution show that the emission lifetime of the species with the short lifetime is only marginally affected by solvent deuteration, which provides $q = 0$ within experimental error (Table 1). The emission lifetimes of the major component recorded in H_2O and D_2O solutions afford q values close to 1 (0.7 – 0.8), suggesting that the main species present in solution contains one coordinated water molecule.

Figure 5. Emission decay profiles recorded in H_2O solutions of the Eu^{3+} complex at different pH values (5×10^{-5} M, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 273$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 613$ nm). The red lines correspond to the fit of the data according to single (pH = 4.8) and double (pH 9.3) exponential decay functions.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of the reduced ^{17}O transverse relaxation rates measured at 11.75 T (9.4 mM). The solid lines through the data points were calculated with the parameters shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Relative intensities of the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_j$ transitions ($J = 1$ and 2), luminescence lifetimes and hydration numbers of the Eu^{3+} complex recorded at different pH values.^a

	$\Delta J = 1 / \Delta J = 2$	$\tau_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} / \text{ms}$	$\tau_{\text{D}_2\text{O}} / \text{ms}$	q
pH 4.5	0.50	0.380(4)	2.126(1)	$2.3^b / 2.1^c$
pH 9.5	0.36	$\tau_1 = 0.290(2)$ (30%) $\tau_2 = 0.683(9)$ (70%)	$\tau_1 = 0.320(2)$ (15%) $\tau_2 = 1.766(3)$ (85%)	$0.1^b / 0.0^c$ $0.8^b / 0.7^c$

^a Eu^{3+} concentration 5×10^{-5} , $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 273$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 613$ nm. ^b Determined according to ref⁸⁴. ^c Determined according to ref⁸³.

Table 2. Parameters obtained from the simultaneous analysis of ^{17}O NMR and ^1H NMRD data.

	GdL (pH 4.98)	GdL (pH 9.20)	GdPCTA ^b	GdDOTA ^c
r_{lp} at 25/37 °C / $\text{mM}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ ^b (20 MHz)	8.3/6.9	6.7/5.2	6.9/ <i>d</i>	4.7/3.8
$k_{\text{ex}}^{298} / 10^6 \text{s}^{-1}$	131 ± 1.3	84 ± 0.8	14.3	4.1
$\Delta H^\ddagger / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	19.1 ± 1.3	18.8 ± 1.5	45	49.8
τ_R^{298} / ps	85 ± 4	122 ± 5	70	77
$E_r / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	20.7 ± 1.3	20.9 ± 1.1	<i>d</i>	16.1
τ_v^{298} / ps	80 ± 5	106 ± 6.0	28	11
$E_v / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	1.0^a	1.0^a	3.6	1.0^a
$D_{\text{GdH}}^{298} / 10^{-10} \text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	22.4^a	22.4^a	22.4^a	22
$E_{\text{DGdH}} / \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	20^a	20^a	<i>d</i>	20.2
$\Delta^2 / 10^{19} \text{s}^{-2}$	1.06 ± 0.3	0.69 ± 0.2	2.8	1.6
$A/\hbar / 10^6 \text{rad s}^{-1}$	-3.8^a	-3.8^a	-3.8^a	-3.7
$r_{\text{GdH}} / \text{Å}$	3.1^a	3.1^a	3.1^a	3.1^a
$a_{\text{GdH}} / \text{Å}$	3.8^a	$3.8^{[a]}$	3.8^a	3.5^a
q^{298}	2^a	1^a	2^a	1^a

^a Parameters fixed during the fitting procedure. ^b Data from reference⁸⁵. ^c Data from reference⁸⁶. ^d Not reported.

Figure 7. Superposed ^1H DOSY (D_2O , 500 MHz, 298 K) experiments of YL recorded at pH 5.0 (blue) and 9.0 (red).

^{17}O NMR studies and parameters determining r_{1p} . The observed relaxivities depend upon a relatively large number of parameters, and thus it is important to obtain information about some of them using independent techniques.⁸⁷ We therefore measured ^{17}O NMR transverse relaxation rates, which provide direct information on the exchange rate of the coordinated water molecules. The reduced transverse relaxation rates present an almost linear variation with the inverse temperature (Figure 6). The positive slope indicates that the system is in the fast exchange regime over the whole range of accessible temperatures, pointing to a fast water exchange.^{88,89}

A simultaneous fit of the ^1H NMRD profiles and ^{17}O NMR relaxation data was carried out to estimate the parameters governing relaxivity both at high and low pH. The analysis of the data was performed by fixing some parameters to reasonable values: 1) The distance between the proton nuclei of coordinated water molecules and the Gd^{3+} ion was fixed to 3.1 Å following previous NMRD and ENDOR studies;^{86,90} 2) The distance of closest approach of a second sphere water molecule, which affects the outer-sphere contribution to relaxivity, was fixed at 3.8 Å;⁹¹ 3) The diffusion coefficient D_{GdH}^{298} and its activation energy E_{DGdH} were fixed to reasonable values of ($D_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{298} = 22.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $E_{\text{DH}_2\text{O}} = 20 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$;⁹² 4) The activation energy for the modulation of the zero-field splitting energy was set to 1 kJ mol^{-1} ;^{86,93} 5) The value for the ^{17}O scalar hyperfine coupling constant (A/\hbar), which was shown to be little affected by the nature of the ligand coordinated to Gd^{3+} , was fixed to the standard value of $-3.8 \times 10^6 \text{ rad s}^{-1}$;^{94,95} 6) Finally, the number of water molecules coordinated to the Gd^{3+} ion was fixed to $q = 2$ at pH 4.98 and $q = 1$ at pH 9.20 on the grounds of the hydration numbers determined for the Eu^{3+} analogue from luminescence lifetime measurements. At high

pH luminescence measurements indicate the presence of at least two species in solution with different hydration numbers, with the major species being that with $q = 1$. Thus, the results of the fits of ^1H and ^{17}O relaxation data at high pH need to be taken with some care.

The ^{17}O NMR relaxation data and ^1H NMRD profiles could be fitted well with the parameters shown in Table 2. The water exchange of the coordinated water molecules is rather fast, particularly at pH 4.98. At this pH k_{ex}^{298} is one order of magnitude faster than for the bis-hydrated GdPCTA complex,⁸⁵ and more than 30 times faster than for GdDOTA .⁸⁶ The water exchange rate is somewhat reduced at pH 9.2, but remains very high. The value of τ_{R} obtained at low pH is very similar to those reported for GdPCTA and GdDOTA , which are expected to present similar hydrodynamic radii. At high pH τ_{R} is longer, which suggests a certain degree of aggregation in solution (see below). Finally, the parameters that define the relaxation of the electron spin: The mean square zero-field-splitting energy (Δ^2) and its correlation time (τ_c), take values comparable to those determined for Gd^{3+} complexes of PCTA and DOTA derivatives (Table 2).

NMR and DFT studies. ^1H NMR studies were carried out using solutions of the diamagnetic Y^{3+} complex at pH values of 5.0 and 9.0. The ionic radii and coordination chemistry of Gd^{3+} and Y^{3+} are very similar, and thus Y^{3+} complexes can be used as diamagnetic subrogates of the Gd^{3+} analogues.⁹⁶ The spectrum recorded at pH 5.0 is reasonably well resolved, and shows three signals for the aromatic proton nuclei of the pyridyl unit at 7.89, 7.39 and 7.33 ppm. The signals due to aliphatic proton nuclei are observed in the range 1.8–4.4 ppm and are relatively broad at room temperature. Diffusion Or-

dered Spectroscopy (DOSY) experiments show that all ^1H NMR signals resonate along a single diffusion value of $3.63 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Figure 7). This diffusion coefficient is similar to those determined previously in D_2O solution for small lanthanide complexes displaying discrete structures in solution. The use of the Stokes–Einstein equation for translation provides a van der Waals radius of 5.49 Å.

Figure 8. Optimized geometry of $[\text{GdHL}]$ obtained with DFT calculations. Hydrogen atoms attached to carbon atoms are omitted for simplicity.

DFT calculations were carried out to gain information on the structure of the Gd^{3+} complex of L upon protonation (see computational details below). The model system used included two inner-sphere water molecules, in line with the results obtained from luminescence and relaxometric data. Four explicit second-sphere water molecules were also included in the model to improve the description of the $\text{Gd}-\text{O}_{\text{water}}$ bonds, following previous computational studies.⁹⁷ Given that GdPCTA derivatives are known to contain two inner-sphere water molecules, it is reasonable to assume that a donor atom of the iminodiacetate group coordinates to the metal ion, as otherwise a higher hydration number would be expected (i. e. GdPC2A shows a higher hydration number than GdPCTA).⁶⁷ Complex protonation ($\text{p}K_{\text{a}} = 7.01$, see above) must occur at the amine N atom of the iminodiacetate group. Our DFT calculations provide a minimum energy structure that is in line with this reasoning (Figure 8). The metal ion is coordinated to the four N atoms of the macrocyclic fragment, two oxygen atoms of the acetate groups and two oxygen atoms of two inner-sphere water molecules (Table S2, Supporting Information). Nine-coordination is completed by an oxygen atom of the iminodiacetate moiety. The protonated N atom of the iminodiacetate group is involved in hydrogen bond interactions with two oxygen atoms of carboxylate groups. A similar coordination was suggested for a DO3A derivative containing a protonated aminophosphonate group on the basis of spectroscopic studies.⁹⁸

The molecular volume of the $[\text{GdHL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system, estimated as the volume inside a contour of 0.001 electron Bohr⁻³ of the electron density, is 729.5 Å³. The radius of the complex can be estimated to be 5.24 Å considering a sphere of

the same volume. This value is in excellent agreement with the one estimated from the measured diffusion coefficient (5.49 Å), confirming the discrete nature of the complex in solution.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the Y^{3+} complex recorded at pH 9.0 is more complex than that recorded at low pH (Figure 8). The aliphatic region is poorly resolved, while four signals are clearly observed for the three proton nuclei of the pyridyl ring, which evidences the presence of more than one complex species in solution. The corresponding DOSY spectrum reveals the presence of four major species with diffusion coefficients of $3.04 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $2.53 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $2.10 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $1.60 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which correspond to van der Waals radii of 6.55, 7.87, 9.49 and 12.45 Å. These results suggest that at basic pH the complex forms small aggregates in solution, presumably due to intermolecular coordination of the iminodiacetate group. This intermolecular coordination reduces the number of water molecules coordinated to the metal ion, yielding $q = 0$ and $q = 1$ species, as suggested by luminescence lifetime measurements. Coordination of the negatively charged iminodiacetate unit is also consistent with the spectral changes observed in the emission spectra of the Eu^{3+} complex upon increasing pH. A few examples of Ln^{3+} complexes that form stable aggregates in solution assembled through bridging carboxylate units have been reported in the literature.^{99–101} The formation of these aggregates does not cause loss of pH-dependency of relaxivity, as reported recently for GdDO3A -arylsulfonamide complexes.¹⁰²

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have reported a Gd^{3+} complex with an interesting relaxivity pH response associated with a change in the number of water molecules coordinated to the metal ion. The protonation of the complex occurs in the biologically relevant 6.0–8.0 pH range, and involves the exocyclic N atom of the ligand. DFT and spectroscopic studies suggest that at low pH the iminodiacetate moiety of the ligand remains coordinated to the Ln^{3+} ion through one of the carboxylate oxygen atoms. Upon deprotonation, the iminodiacetate unit allows intermolecular coordination and formation of small aggregates, resulting in a reduced hydration number. The results reported in this paper represent one of the few examples of Ln^{3+} complexes for which the formation of stable aggregates in solution has been established. However, it is likely that many other coordinatively unsaturated Ln^{3+} complexes also undergo aggregation in solution, suggesting that this possibility must be considered with much more caution than is usually taking at the moment.

EXPERIMENTAL AND COMPUTATIONAL SECTION

Materials. 2-(3,6,9-Triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-yl)ethan-1-amine (PYTREN) was synthesized as described previously.^{70,71} All other reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification.

Spectroscopic studies. The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligand and intermediates were recorded on a Bruker Advance DRX 300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz for ^1H and at 75.4 MHz for ^{13}C . MS analysis was performed under ESI conditions on a LCT Premier mass spectrometer. The Eu^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Y^{3+} complexes were prepared by mixing stoichio-

metric amounts of $\text{LnCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with an aqueous solution of the ligand while maintaining the pH at 6 by addition of 1 M NaOH. The pH of the final solutions was adjusted with diluted HCl and NaOH solutions. ^1H NMR spectra of the Eu^{3+} complex were recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at 300 MHz for ^1H . DOSY spectra of the Y^{3+} complex were recorded using a Bruker Avance 500 MHz spectrometer equipped with a dual $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ cryoprobe. The ^1H $1/T_1$ NMRD profiles were obtained with a fast field-cycling Stellar Smart-Tracer relaxometer (Mede, Pavia, Italy) varying the magnetic field strength from 0.00024 to 0.25 T, which corresponds to proton Larmor frequency range of 0.01–10 MHz. The instrument operates under computer control providing $1/T_1$ values with an absolute uncertainty of $\pm 1\%$. Temperature was controlled with a Stellar VTC-91 airflow heater equipped with a calibrated copper–constantan thermocouple (uncertainty of ± 0.1 K). Additional data at higher field (20–60 MHz) were obtained using a Stellar Relaxometer coupled to a Bruker WP80 NMR electromagnet reconditioned for variable-field measurements (15–80 MHz proton Larmor frequency). The concentration of the complex was determined using Bulk Magnetic Susceptibility (BMS) shift measurements performed at 11.7 T. ^{17}O NMR spectra were acquired on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer (11.7 T) using a 5 mm probe and standard temperature control. An aqueous solution of the complexes (9.4 mM) was enriched to reach 2.0% of the ^{17}O isotope (Cambridge Isotope). The transverse relaxation rates were measured from the signal width at half-height.

Excitation and emission spectra in the UV–vis region were obtained with a Horiba FluoroMax Plus-P spectrofluorometer equipped with a 150 W ozone-free xenon arc lamp and a R928P photon counting emission detector, as well as a photodiode reference detector for monitoring lamp output. All spectra were corrected for the instrumental response. An integration time of 0.1 s was used in all steady state measurements. Luminescence decays were measured using the Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) module of the same instrument using a xenon flash lamp.

2,2'-(2-(3,9-Bis(carboxymethyl)-3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-yl)ethyl)azanediyl)diacetic acid (H₄L). Chloroacetic acid (11.7 mmol) and KOH (11.7 mmol) were added to an aqueous solution of 2-(3,6,9-triaza-1(2,6)-pyridinacyclodecaphane-6-yl)ethan-1-amine (PYTREN, 2.6 mmol) at pH 10 adjusted with 0.1 M KOH. The mixture was refluxed for 24 hours. After 24 hours the mixture was cooled down at room temperature and then the solution neutralized with KOH. The solution was concentrated and loaded onto an ion-exchange resin (Dowex 1x8-400). The column was washed with H_2O and the product was eluted with a 0.02M formic acid solution to afford a white solid product. ^1H NMR (D_2O , 300 MHz): δ_{H} 2.89 (bs, 4H), 3.07 (bm, 2H), 3.51 (bm, 6H), 3.95 (s, 4H), 4.13 (s, 4H), 4.82 (s, 4H), 7.45 (d, $^3J=7.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.96 (t, $^3J=7.5$ Hz, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (D_2O , 75 MHz): δ_{C} 56.4, 57.6, 61.9, 65.5, 65.9, 68.1, 68.4, 131.2, 131.6, 148.6, 158.2, 178.1, 178.2. HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_5\text{O}_8$ 480.2100; found 480.2109. MS-ES: m/z 482 ($\text{M} + \text{H}^+$); 504.2 ($\text{M} + \text{Na}^+$).

Crystal structure determination. 0.1 mmol of H₄L were dissolved in pure water and ethanol vapor was diffused into

the vessel. Colorless crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained after four days. The crystals were measured in a Bruker D8 Venture X-ray diffractometer using $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) equipped with an Oxford low temperature unit operating at 130 K. Indexing, strategy and data collection were performed with APEX3 software suite. OLEX2 was used as frontend for solving and refining.¹⁰³ The initial structure was solved with direct methods using SIR2014.¹⁰⁴ The resulting structure was refined with SHELXL2014.¹⁰⁵ Initially, an isotropic refinement was performed on the non-hydrogen atoms and then anisotropic refinement was introduced. Hydrogen atoms H2, H4 and H5 which are the ones placed onto nitrogen atoms, were found in the Fourier map and their positions were left free in the refinement. The rest of hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions. Two soft restraints were placed to orient properly water moieties containing O10 and O12. Crystal data and structure refinement details: Formula: $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{31}\text{N}_5\text{O}_8 \cdot 4.272\text{H}_2\text{O}$; MW: 558.34; crystal system: monoclinic; space group: $\text{P2}_1/\text{c}$; $a = 14.7386(14) \text{ \AA}$; $b = 13.7004(13) \text{ \AA}$; $c = 12.9591(11) \text{ \AA}$; $\beta = 90.009(3)^\circ$; $V = 2616.8(4) \text{ \AA}^3$; $F(000) = 1195$; $Z = 4$; $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.420 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $\mu = 0.117 \text{ mm}^{-1}$; θ range = $2.57 - 28.20^\circ$; $R_{\text{int}} = 0.0910$; 52998 measured reflections, of which 5422 were independent and 6544 were unique with $I > 2\sigma(I)$. GOF on $F^2 = 1.037$; $R1 = 0.0422$; $wR2$ (all data) = 0.1042; Largest differences peak and hole: 0.210 and $-0.259 \text{ e \AA}^{-3}$.

DFT calculations. All DFT calculations were carried out by using the Gaussian 09 package (Revision E.01)^{ref} within the hybrid meta-GGA approximation with the TPSSH exchange-correlation functional.^{106,107} Solvent effects were included using the integral-equation formalism variant of the polarizable continuum model (IEFPCM).¹⁰⁸ The 6–31G(d,p) basis set was used for C, H, N and O, while Gd was described with the large-core quasi-relativistic effective core potential approximation and the associated [5s4p3d]-GTO valence-basis set.¹⁰⁹ Geometry optimizations were followed by frequency calculations to confirm the nature of the optimized geometries as local minima.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the [ACS Publications website](#) at DOI: XXXXX. Additional crystallographic and DFT data (PDF).

Accession codes

CCDC 1884191 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: +44 1223 336033.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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TOC Graphic:

A new Gd^{3+} complex with a scoriand ligand exhibits an interesting relaxivity pH response associated with a change in the number of water molecules coordinated to the metal ion. Deprotonation of the ligand allows intermolecular coordination and formation of small aggregates, resulting in a reduced hydration number.
